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NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/>.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports the activities developed within task 9.1, focusing on the analysis of physical ocean forecasting improvements produced by larger numbers of NAUTILOS-like observations.

Three different study sites were used, with different geographical scales and ocean dynamics: The Mediterranean Sea, the SW-Iberian coast and the Hardanger Fjord coastal system. This diversity assures generality of the results and conclusions obtained. Diversity on the models and the data assimilation techniques used also contribute to this diversity.

Since no NAUTILOS-Like data was available at the beginning of the project, the methodology chosen to evaluate the impact of data on ocean forecasting capabilities was that of Observing System Simulation Experiments (OSSE). The OSSE methodology uses two different model setups for each study site, one being of higher quality and producing results closer to the nature than the other. This higher quality model is named Nature Run (NR) and is assumed to represent the reality for the sake of the experiments. The second, lower quality model, is named the Free Run (FR) and is used to assimilate data from the NR, as if they were observations taken from the nature (named Synthetic Observations). The improvement of the FR forecast when different sets of synthetic observations are assimilated is assessed by comparison with the NR. For these experiments to be possible, robust assimilation algorithms must be put in place for each model. In the Mediterranean Sea study site, the existing Hybrid EnKF assimilation algorithm was improved and adapted, to allow assimilation of data in vertical profiles. In the other two study sites the models didn't use assimilation techniques before NAUTILOS, thus an EnOI methodology was implemented in the SW-Iberia site and a 4DVar methodology was implemented in the Hardanger Fjord site.

Different data assimilation experiments were conducted in the different sites, exploring the effects on forecasting quality of larger quantities and types of observations being delivered by NAUTILOS-like low-cost sensors and their associated platforms.

Results shown that larger datasets of observed variables lead to more accurate ocean forecasts. In fact, the application of the OSSE methodology in different regional domains, with different ocean dynamics, using different models and different assimilation methods have all produced the same result: an increase in the number of observations available to assimilate in the models produce an increase in the quality of the forecast.

This conclusion supports the activities developed within NAUTILOS, since lower cost sensors and more efficient platforms will contribute to a more precise and longer-range ocean forecasting systems. A broad estimation of the improvement in forecasting quality produced by a full adoption of NAUTILOS technologies in future ocean observing efforts lies around 40%. Improvements depend on the site and on the observational strategy selected. Generically results have shown that a good balance and diversity in observational methodologies give the best results. It is thus advisable to combine fixed observations with profiles measurements, use of autonomous underwater vehicles, and others. Also, in terms of variables measured, a higher diversity gives best results.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
4DVar	4-Dimensional Variational assimilation
EnKF	Ensemble Kalman Filter
ENOI	Ensemble Optimal Interpolation
OSSE	Observing System Simulation Experiment
RMSD (RMSE)	Root Mean Square Deviation (Error)
NR	Nature Run
FM	Forecast Model
AM	Assimilation Model
RRMSD	Relative Root Mean Square Deviation
SSH	Sea Surface Height
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
SAL	Salinity
TEM	Temperature

I. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable describes the activities developed in Task 9.1 regarding the construction and use of three physical oceanographic models to evaluate the impact of NAUTILOS new observing technologies in the forecast of different coastal and ocean environments. Three models were adapted for this purpose: The POSEIDON operational system, operated by HCMR and covering the entire Mediterranean Sea; the SOMA operational system, operated by UAlg and covering the SW Iberian Coast and the ROHO operational system, operated by NIVA and covering the Hardangerfjord and adjacent coastal region in Norway. The impact of new NAUTILOS observing technologies on forecasting models is assessed prior to the existence of the observations by using the concept of Observing System Simulation Experiments (OSSE). The background of this methodology was defined in WP8 and detailed in Deliverable D8.6. In Task 9.1 most of the methodology delineated in D8.6 was applied, with some small adaptations which are detailed in subsequent sections. The use of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers for ocean observation, as advocated by NAUTILOS, is expected to improve model forecasting capabilities. The results obtained in this task and reported in this deliverable confirms this expectation. It is also shown that a saturation exists for the improvement regarding the number of observations and that the type and location where the new observation is performed influences the forecasting improvement. The use of the OSSE concept allows to extract that information from conceptual, model driven experiments, prior to the existence of actual observations, as described in D8.6.

In the next section, a brief description of the OSSE methodology and the modelling options defined in D8.6 is presented to allow a standalone reading of the document. A description of the methodologies applied for each of the three pilot sites is then presented, followed by results and discussion.

II. SUMMARY OF D8.6 AND OBJECTIVES

This section recalls the basic methodology defined in D8.6 for the application of Observing System Simulation Experiments (OSSE) as well as the different metrics defined to assess model forecast performance. The objective is to allow a standalone reading of the document without the need for referring to the previous deliverable. For a more detailed and in-depth analysis of the concepts, the reading of D8.6 is suggested.

The objective of Task T9.1 reported in this deliverable is to assess the improvement in the forecasting capabilities of ocean and coastal physical models produced by the introduction of NAUTILOS-like observations (i.e. large quantity of cost-effective observations). This assessment is a difficult task since the observations do not exist yet, and it is very expensive to set up ocean trials for that purpose. Acknowledging that, the concept of OSSE was proposed. The main conceptual idea behind an OSSE is the substitution of the reality, which is difficult and expensive to observe, by a numerical simulation of very good quality. This simulation is commonly known as the Nature Run (NR). The NR is used as if it was the reality, and observations are extracted from it. These are the so called “Synthetic Observations”. In parallel, a forecasting model with lower resolution is setup, assimilating the synthetic observations. The “goodness” of the forecast is assessed against the NR, using a set of evaluation parameters and metrics. OSSE are thus “data denial” experiments Halliwell et al. (2014, 2015).

Figure 1 summarizes the common framework of the OSSE that will be developed in this task. The concept of “fraternal twin” experiments will be used, meaning that the same numerical method will be used both for the NR and for the forecasting model. The NR will have a spatial resolution which will be higher than the resolution used in the forecasting run. Additionally, the forcing and the parameterizations used can be different. The NR is run from $t = 0$ to $t = T_f$, either continuously assimilating real observations or restarting periodically from global circulation models which assimilate real observations. This is still common practice for local and regional models.

A free run of the forecasting model, without any assimilation is then executed. This is the reference forecasting run against which improvements due to assimilation of synthetic observations are compared. Two sets of experiments will then be conducted: The Pre-NAUTILOS runs and the post-NAUTILOS runs. Both sets of experiments assimilate synthetic observations from the NR. The type and characteristics of the synthetic observations used in each set of experiments will characterize the status-quo of observations of that set of experiments. The Pre-NAUTILOS scenarios will characterize the present situation in terms of in situ and remote sensing observations. The Post-NAUTILOS scenarios will be characterized by a larger number of in situ observations, closer distributed in space, as well as in time. The precision of the observations is as important as their values for assimilation in ocean models. The Post-NAUTILOS scenarios will use foreseen precisions for the sensors being developed within the project. Also, the results from NAUTILOS are foreseen to improve calibration of remote sensing products, rendering more accurate measurements of remote sensing variables. This will also be accounted for when creating the post-NAUTILOS scenarios.

As shown in Figure 1 the results from the experiments using the forecasting models must be compared with the NR. These comparisons will enable to assess the expected improvements to be obtained from NAUTILOS. A set of metrics were defined in Deliverable D8.6 to be used case by case in the three pilot sites, according to the needs of each

experiment performed. Below, those metrics are summarized. A more detailed explanation of the metrics can be found in D8.6.

Figure 1 – Common framework used in NAUTILOS for the implementation of the Observing System Simulation Experiments (OSSE) (Based on Fig. 8; D8.6).

Spatially Integrated Averages and Standard Deviations

Instantaneous spatial averages (AVG) and standard deviations (STD) of both the NR and the forecasting model results can be used to plot timeseries of model evolution:

$$AVG(t_i) = \frac{\sum_{domain} \theta(t_i)}{N} \quad (1)$$

$$STD(t_i) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{domain} (\theta(t_i) - AVG(t_i))^2}{N}} \quad (2)$$

Where θ is the variable under analysis in time t_i and N is the number of model cells used for the spatial average.

Spatially Integrated RMSD

Instantaneous spatially integrated root mean square deviation (RMSD) between the NR and the forecasting model results can be used to plot timeseries with evolution of model comparisons:

$$RMSD(t_i) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{domain} (\theta_f(t_i) - \theta_{NR}(t_i))^2}{N}} \quad (3)$$

Where θ_f and θ_{NR} are the forecast and NR variable being assessed in time t_i and N has the same meaning as above.

Temporally Integrated Averages and Standard deviations

The temporally integrated average can be applied to a single point and is computed by:

$$AVG(i, j, k) = \frac{\sum_{t_i=0}^T \theta(i, j, k)}{T} \quad (4)$$

The same logic can be used to compute the standard deviations:

$$STD(i, j, k) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t_i=0}^T (\theta(i, j, k) - AVG(i, j, k))^2}{T}} \quad (5)$$

Temporally Integrated RMSD

Using the same rationale, the root mean square deviation between the forecast and the NR is computed by:

$$RMSD(i, j, k) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t_i=0}^T (\theta_f(i, j, k) - \theta_{NR}(i, j, k))^2}{T}} \quad (6)$$

Murphy Skill Score

Maps of forecast skill can be constructed using the Murphy (1988) skill score:

$$\Sigma = \rho^2 - \left[\rho - \frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_{NR}} \right]^2 - \left[\frac{(\bar{\theta}_f - \bar{\theta}_{NR})}{\sigma_{NR}} \right]^2 \quad (7)$$

Σ is applied to every grid cell during the analysed time period, to produce the skill map. ρ is the correlation between NR and the forecast, σ is the standard deviation and $\bar{\theta}$ is the average of the property being analysed. Note that Σ can assume negative values. According to Murphy (1988), values of $\Sigma < 0$ denote a “not significant” skill while values of $\Sigma > 0$ correspond to “significant skill”. A “perfect skill” would correspond to a value of $\Sigma = 1$.

Taylor Diagrams

Taylor diagrams (Taylor, 2001) combine different statistics, comparing the forecast and the NR in a single diagram. Figure 2 represents a sample Taylor diagram. Forecast model results are represented by the coloured circles and triangles and are compared with the NR result, represented by the hollow black circumference. The radial distance to the centre measures the standard deviation of model results, normalised by the standard deviation of the NR. The angle of the dotted isolines above the horizontal measures the correlation between the model forecast and the NR and the grey isolines centred in the NR black circle measure the RMS difference of the forecast relative to the NR, normalized also by the standard deviation of the NR.

Figure 2 - Sample of a simple Taylor diagram. Forecast model results represented by the coloured circles and triangles are compared with the NR result, represented by the hollow black circumference.

This diagram can be applied to spatially integrated time series of model variables (e.g., T, S, u, v). Generically, the closer the forecast result is to the NR the better is the model performance. The three statistics can however be evaluated separately, giving a broader insight of the model behaviour.

III. METHODOLOGY

MEDITERRANEAN

The Mediterranean basin scale hydrodynamic model is based on the Princeton Ocean Model (POM) (<http://www.ccpo.odu.edu/POMWEB>; Blumberg and Mellor, 1983), which is a 3-D sigma-coordinate, free surface, primitive equation circulation model that is currently operational within the HCMR's forecast system POSEIDON (<https://poseidon.hcmr.gr>; Korres et al, 2007). The model forecast variables are temperature, salinity, velocity, sea surface height and turbulent kinetic energy. A detailed description of the implemented calculation schemes, structure and input data can be found in Deliverable 8.6.

The impact of the NAUTILOS observational strategies on the hydrodynamic simulation and forecasting model skill has been evaluated through the performance of OSSE. To perform the OSSE, two basin-scale models of the Mediterranean Sea have been developed: MED20 with a horizontal resolution of $1/20^\circ \times 1/20^\circ$ (~5 km) representing the natural run (NR) and MED10 with a lower resolution of $1/10^\circ \times 1/10^\circ$ (~10 km), the forecast model (FM), which is used to perform the OSSE simulations. Both models have 24 sigma-layers in the vertical direction, a common atmospheric forcing obtained from the POSEIDON operational weather forecast, using a properly tuned bulk formulae set for the calculation of momentum, heat and freshwater fluxes at the air-sea interface (Korres and Lascaratos, 2003). They also share the same lateral boundary (Gibraltar and Dardanelles straits, river inputs) conditions. MED20 model was initialised from MED10 model output on January 2010, followed by a 5-year (2010-2014) spin-up simulation. After that, a simulation with MED20 over 2010 was repeated, providing the synthetic observations, which are assimilated by the FM in the OSSE. Thus, the initial conditions of the NR and FM simulations are different to ensure that the two simulations are sufficiently different for the purpose of the OSSE.

Figure 3 - Mean annual sea surface height and water circulation derived for one year simulation (2010) of POSEIDON hydrodynamic model with $1/10^\circ \times 1/10^\circ$ (MED10) and $1/20^\circ \times 1/20^\circ$ (MED20) grid resolution.

The implemented OSSE methodology consists of sampling synthetic data from the NR model and assimilating it to the FM. To achieve this, a hybrid ensemble Kalman filter (EnKF) data assimilation scheme is employed that combines a flow-dependent error covariance estimated from a stochastically generated ensemble (Singular Evolutive Interpolated Kalman filter, SEIK) with a static background covariance constructed from a set of empirical orthogonal functions (Singular Fixed Extended Kalman filter, SFEK) (Tsiaras et al., 2017). In this way, the computations include a small number of ensemble members, while the rest of the basis remains fixed. Localisation is also used to filter out long-range correlations and allow more

degrees of freedom to fit the data (Nerger et al., 2006), using data within a specified cut-off radius set at ~ 50 km. The synthetic data sampled from the NR include sea surface temperature (SST) and sea surface height (SSH), as well as water column profiles of temperature (TEM) and salinity (SAL). Given that synthetic data sampled from the NR mimic real observations, a perturbation was applied to account for instrument uncertainties and random representation errors. Thus, an observation error was introduced on synthetic data from the NR, adding a Gaussian-distributed random perturbation, with standard deviations (STD) of 0.03 m for sea surface height, 0.5°C for temperature, and 0.05 psu for salinity. All simulations of OSSE had the same start date of 01-01-2010, simulation period of one year and model timestep of 20 min.

A series of annual simulation experiments were carried out, implementing different assimilation strategies and sampling data characteristics. Specifically, the assimilation experiments included:

- sampling of surface data only (SSH/SST), profile data only (TEM/SAL) and their combination,
- different observation error for the assimilated data.
- different scenarios of sampling point selection for salinity and temperature profiles, including real in situ data positions, uniform gridded distribution or random selection (see Figure 4). For the first case, representative real data locations were obtained from the Copernicus CMEMS In Situ TAC actual data for years 2016-2019 (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/el/about/producers/insitu-tac>).
- different sampling rates, e.g. every 8 or 16 days.
- different number of assimilated profiles, from none (assimilation of surface data only) to the whole domain (i.e., 11169 grid points)
- optimum selection of profile locations according to best improvement criteria, i.e., minimizing the RMSD error from the NR. This process was based on the calculation of the RMSD from a series of assimilation experiments with increasing number of TEM/SAL profile points from the NR and subsequent redistribution of the sampling points based on the improvement of different parameters (temperature, salinity, density, mixed layer depth, etc.)

Figure 4 - Distinct types of assimilation point selection. The dots represent the position of synthetic observations from the NR. The figure shows the positions of the total unique TEM/SAL profiles in 2016 according to the CMEMS In Situ TAC database (left), random (middle) and gridded (right) selection of the same number of points.

The different assimilation model runs (AM) were evaluated against the NR, as well as for their overall improvement compared to the free run of the model (FM). Moreover, an algorithm for objectively selecting regions, characterized by higher variability, where data assimilation had a more significant contribution to the model skill, was developed. This allowed to better define the optimum observing strategies and quantify improvements on data products.

SW IBERIAN COAST

The Algarve Operational Modelling and Monitoring System, or simply SOMA, is a high-resolution operational model designed to forecast SW Iberian Coast dynamics. The model was developed based on the MOHID Modelling System environment (Leitão et al., 2005; Martins et al., 2001; Neves, 2007). SOMA system arose from the need to produce a high-resolution model in order to provide predictions of the sea state and the trajectory of oil spills on the Algarve coast (Janeiro et al., 2012, 2017), using MOHID oil spill model with the Lagrangian transport approach. Besides forecasting oil spills, it was also evaluated the efficiency of downscaling methods in determining the sources of oil leakage by combining backtracking simulation with vessel trajectories. As a result, SOMA is a validated model and is operational since July 2019 (Mendonça et al., 2023) making predictions of the hydrodynamic behavior and water properties of the implemented region.

The operational model encompasses two levels of increasing resolution, using bathymetric data from the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODNET). The first level uses a 2 km horizontal resolution grid and the second a 1 km grid. The implementation area is shown in Figure 5. Both have the same vertical spatial discretization with 50 layers of cartesian coordinates. At the open boundary, a Blumberg & Kantha (1985) condition is applied to the water level and a Flow Relaxation Scheme (FRS) (Martinsen & Engedahl, 1987) is used for velocity, salinity and temperature. Communication between the two levels is performed also using the FRS method, to relax the water level, the zonal and the meridional horizontal velocity components, through an eight-cell band adjacent to the lateral boundary. Simulation step time is 30 and 15 seconds for the first and second levels respectively.

Figure 5 - Bathymetry from the SOMA system, consisting of two levels of resolution: the first on the left with a 2 km grid and the second, implemented in a smaller area, with a 1 km grid resolution.

At the boundary, conditions for temperature, salinity, and current velocities are supplied by Mercator Ocean Analysis and Forecast provided by Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00016>). Since this product does

not include tide explicitly, SOMA has an additional grid to run externally a 2D hydrodynamic model, forced by the FES2014 global tidal solution. This external level has the single purpose of generating and supplying the tidal conditions to level 1. For the atmospheric forcing fields, SOMA uses the results of the regional weather forecast system SKIRON (Kallos et al., 1997; Papadopoulos et al., 2002), provided by Atmospheric Modelling and Weather Forecasting Group of The National and Kapodistrian University of Athens.

Based on the OSSE concept described above, two sets of simulations were created for the SOMA system. The first one, known as the Nature Run (NR), is a one-year simulation using the model's standard bathymetry, without any changes of what is depicted in Figure 5. The second set, the Free Run (FR), is also a one-year simulation for the same period as the NR, but with a 2 km resolution in level 2. This FR serves as a reference for improvements through the assimilation of synthetic observations from the NR. During the experiments both simulations start at the same date, from identical initial conditions, generated by a spin-off simulation, and run for one year, using the same atmospheric and oceanic boundary conditions. The NR serves as the system's truth from which the synthetic observations are extracted. NR possesses weekly adjustments with a new a spin-off simulation initialized from CMEMS data that generates fresh initial conditions for subsequent days.

Synthetic observations are taken from the NR solution. Sea surface temperature (SST) synthetic observations were extracted in different quantities to test the improvement of the system in scenarios with incremental quantities of observations. For this, in each scenario, the NR level 2 domain solution was divided into squared sub-areas from which a single observation is extracted at a random position (Figure 6). The observations are then incorporated into the assimilation step. The Ensemble Optimal Interpolation (EnOI) scheme, which applies the approximation of time-invariant error statistics (Evensen, 2003; Counillon & Bertino, 2009), was used. In this way, the analysis is limited only in the spatial dimension and comes at a small computational overhead. Each observation scenario generates an updated state of the FR solution which is then run for seven more days and then compared with the NR solution using the metrics described in chapter II.

Figure 6 - Extraction of synthetic observations from NR, represented by the red dots. The outer dotted line represents the level 1 domain, while the inner dotted line represents level 2. The difference between “A” and “B” is the size of the sub-areas chosen for extraction: 10 observations in “A” from squares with sides composed by 45 grid cells, and 200 in “B” using squares with sides composed by 10 grid cells.

HARDANGER FJORD SYSTEM

The ROHO system is a model system aimed at the Hardanger Fjord in southern Norway. The fjord is the fifth longest in the world and contains several marine protected areas. The wider Hardanger fjord region area is also an important aquaculture production area with more than 40,000 tonnes of atlantic salmon and rainbow trout produced annually.

The model implementations for the OSSE comprise two ROMS (Shchepetkin et al., 2005; Moore et al., 2004) models on regular grids; an 800m resolution model for the pre- and post-nautilus experiments (ROHO800) along with the nature run on a different grid with 160m resolution (ROHO160). The grid extents differ slightly between the two models, but both cover the entire Hardanger fjord system (Figure 7).

The ROHO800 model was set up with 4d-var data assimilation and coupled with the ERSEM biogeochemical model. ROHO800 is derived as a subset of another model, NorKyst800 (Kristensen and Gusdal, 2021), which covers the entire Norwegian coast. NorKyst-800 is used operationally in Norwegian Meteorological Institute (met.no). ROHO800 setup has 318 grid points in I-direction, 229 in J-direction, and 25 vertical layers, whilst ROHO160 has 1440 grid points in I-direction, 960 in J-direction, and 25 vertical layers. For both ROHO160 and ROHO800 the initial and boundary conditions for the ocean physics (temperature, salinity, circulation) were derived from GLORYS12V1 (Lellouche et al. 2018). Atmospheric forcing for ROHO800 was prepared from (ERA-Interim, 2009), which is an archive of global atmospheric reanalysis ranging from 1989 to present. The tidal forcing applied in ROHO800 is based on a global inverse barotropic model of ocean tides, TPXO7.26 (Egbert et al. 1994, Egbert and Erofeeva 2002). The river runoff in ROHO800 is from a modelled discharge by NVE (Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate).

The ROHO800 setup had not been run in an assimilative manner before. There are multiple different schemes in the ROMS model for assimilation. As was proposed in WP 8.6 we chose to use the Incremental Strong constraint 4D-Variational (IS4DVAR) because it was the simplest to configure 4d-var scheme available in ROMS and a good start point. The assimilative scheme is computationally intensive and required multiple runs to test settings, so the period chosen to study was a spring season. This was chosen as the most relevant to the biological system with the onset of spring blooms. ROHO160 high-resolution model was used to generate the data for pre and post Nautilus scenarios. This setup was described in the WP 8.6 deliverable.

Synthetic observations were taken from the ROHO160 model based on the assumption of a single mooring as the pre-NAUTILOS setup (which is consistent with the data available from a long term monitoring site in the area) and the post-NAUTILOS observations based on the idea of adding observations from the large number of aquaculture sites within the domain. This was chosen as it is one of the NAUTILOS aims however it could also be considered equivalent to adding large numbers of observations from any in-fjord observing system. There is also a ferry track between Bergen and Stavanger which goes through the outer part of the domain and will be fitted with a ferrybox.

For the OSSE experiment two runs are compared. A pre-NAUTILOS run which assimilates only the synthetic observations from the two permanent mooring stations, and a post-NAUTILOS observation set which includes observations from aquaculture sites (Figure 8a) and from a mimic of the ferrybox platform (Figure 8b).

Figure 7 - Surface temperatures from the ROHO 160 m and ROHO 800 m models.

Figure 8 - Locations of potential observations added during Nautilus within the domain, aquaculture sites (left hand panel) and underway ferrybox (right hand side).

IV. OSSE RESULTS

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Different OSSEs were conducted using synthetic observations from the NR to assess the impact of assimilating satellite and in situ profile data on model performance. Three types of sampling scenarios were tested: (a) assimilation of only SSH/SST data, (b) assimilation of only TEM/SAL profile data, and (c) assimilation of both surface and profile data. Data assimilation improved the model performance in all cases, compared to the free run. The simultaneous assimilation of both surface and profile data yielded the best performance for all examined parameters, combining the advantages of each dataset. Figure 9 shows an example for the RMSD improvement across the entire domain when surface or/and profile data at representative locations (CMEMS In Situ TAC) are included in the assimilation. In this example, the RMSD reduction for the combined assimilation was about 21% for SSH and salinity, and more than 40% for SST and temperature, compared to the FMR. In contrast, when only profile data were assimilated, the improvement did not exceed 20% for all variables, while the assimilation of only SSH/SST data resulted in higher RMSD for salinity.

Figure 9 - Annual SST RMSD across the entire model domain for the free run (FM), the SSH/SST assimilation model (AMssh/sst), the TEM/SAL profile assimilation (AMprof), and their combined assimilation (AMssh/sst&prof). All profile locations from the CMEMS In Situ TAC database for 2016 were used.

The significance of the spatial distribution and amount of assimilated data was investigated by conducting OSSEs with different sampling distributions and varying numbers of assimilated profiles. These included realistic in situ data locations (obtained from CMEMS In Situ TAC existing data), as well as uniformly and randomly scattered points. In all scenarios, the uniform distribution consistently outperformed all other arrangements, as illustrated in Figure 10, even when fewer points were included. This is largely explained by the relatively better spatial coverage, on basin-scale, including areas that are not properly represented by realistic or random in situ data locations (e.g. Adriatic, N. Aegean, S. Ionian).

In another set of OSSE simulations, the impact of measurement uncertainty on the model skill was evaluated, applying a different observation error (i.e. a perturbation with varying amplitude/STD). The introduction of additional errors in the calculations led to a deterioration in the model performance, primarily affecting temperature and salinity profiles, while having a limited impact on sea surface data (see Fig. 11).

Figure 10 - Annual TEM RMSD across the entire model domain (left) and RMSD vertical distribution of salinity and temperature (right), with no profile assimilation (FM), realistic (prof1k, locations obtained from CMEMS In Situ TAC existing data), and uniform (sc1k) distribution of data assimilation profiles.

Figure 11 - Temperature RMSD over time (left) and depth (right), with default (0.5°C, orange lines, AMsc1k-err) and increased (1.5°C, blue lines, AMsc1k-3xerr) observation error, with assimilation of 1260 profiles.

Considering the data assimilation frequency, a decrease in the sampling rate also led to a deterioration in model performance, as expected. As shown in Fig. 12, the RMSD of the AM with a 16-day sampling rate ($AM_{ssh/sst\&prof-16d}$) increased by 34% for TEM compared to the reference simulation with 8-day sampling rate ($AM_{ssh/sst\&prof}$), while the decrease for the other variables was 12% for SSH, 15% for SAL and 31% for SST. A corresponding improvement was observed when the sampling rate increases.

The improvement in the model performance, for each of the four ocean parameters (TEM, SAL, SSH, SST), with the number of assimilated TEM/SAL profiles is shown in Fig.13. This improvement is indicated by the decrease of the total (basin) RMSD, as the number of assimilated points increases. The maximum improvement is achieved, when assimilation is performed across the entire model grid (AM_{max}, 11169 points), reducing the relative RMSD compared to free run (FM, 0 points) by up to 60% for all parameters, except for SSH, which is reduced by 30% (see Fig. 13). The RMSD reach minimum values of 0.03 m for SSH and 0.07 psu for salinity, while SST and TEM have a minimum value of 0.20 °C. Surface parameters (SSH, SST) improve significantly with the assimilation of just 30 profiles, after which the improvement gradually saturates, with notable fluctuations in SSH. The relative RMSD of TEM and SAL decrease more gradually, with temperature improving significantly faster than salinity, as half of the possible RMSD reduction (i.e., 30%) is achieved with 472 profiles for TEM and 634 for SAL, based on exponential decay fitting of the relative RMSD.

Figure 12 - Comparison of the annual average SSH between surface/profile data assimilation models with an 8-day (AM_{ssh/sst&prof}, same as in Fig. 9) and 16-day (AM_{ssh/sst&prof-16d}) sampling rate against the NR (top). The SAL RMSD over time (bottom left) and TEM RMSD over depth (bottom right) are also shown.

Figure 13 - Annual average RMSD (left) and relative RMSD compared to FM (right) over all model domain against the number of the uniformly distributed assimilation points for the considered variables. In the upper right embedded figure, the relative RMSD for the first 140 assimilation points is presented.

Along with the improvement in the model performance with increasing amount of data, it is important to know which areas have a higher contribution in this improvement, therefore,

allowing to design an effective monitoring strategy. Thus, an algorithm was developed to objectively determine the assimilation points that yield the greatest improvement compared to the FM, based on the OSSEs results with varying number of assimilated profiles (see Figure 13). This process aimed to identify the optimal position for a fixed number (110) of TEM/SAL profiles, which may be considered representative for post-NAUTILOS observations (see discussion below). A minimum distance (~6 km) between different points was assumed to prevent oversampling within the same region. The methodology is based on the calculation of the relative annual RMSD ($RRMSD = RRMSD_{AM} / RRMSD_{FM}$) across the entire domain, for AM experiments with different number of assimilation profiles, compared to the free run (FM). A simplified example is shown in Figure 14, illustrating the selection of 110 assimilated positions (yellow dots), within areas with the highest temperature RRMSD improvement of the AM_{max} experiment (data assimilation over the entire model grid), compared to FM.

Figure 14 - Steps for implementing the optimal selection of assimilation points for temperature data across the entire domain. Different colours in the RRMSD map indicate the degree of the FM improvement: black (maximum), red (high), green (moderate), blue (low), and white (minimum).

Several different criteria were tested, using the RRMSD for various parameters and their combinations, including water density (RHO) and mixed layer depth (MLD), as well as for the

combined (sum) and/or the reduction rate (slope) of RRMSD with increasing number of assimilation points. Table 1 summarizes the performance of representative OSSEs based on different selection schemes of 110 profiles, in comparison with the FM and AM of uniformly scattered and randomly selected profiles. The combined RRMSD reduction rate (slope) criterion, used for both of salinity and temperature, outperformed all other assimilation approaches for the ensemble of considered parameters, showing the best results in terms of model improvement (RRMSD decrease, increase of correlation, Murphy score).

Table 1 - Relative RMSD (RRMSD), correlation coefficient (r), and Murphy score (Σ) for AM assimilating surface data and 110 profiles. The highest and second-highest scores are highlighted in red and green, respectively.

Model	SSH			SST			TEM			SAL		
	RRMSD (%)	r	Σ									
FM		0.7765	0.6301		0.9922	0.9920		0.9863	0.9810		0.9614	0.9595
Random	-3.30	0.8972	0.8151	42.56	0.9977	0.9977	20.76	0.9910	0.9905	8.01	0.9741	0.9736
Scatter	0.44	0.9012	0.8340	43.04	0.9978	0.9977	23.34	0.9917	0.9908	10.17	0.9757	0.9750
TEM	6.15	0.8956	0.8361	42.65	0.9977	0.9977	22.07	0.9917	0.9914	8.38	0.9744	0.9733
RHO	4.35	0.8864	0.8184	42.56	0.9978	0.9977	22.85	0.9918	0.9914	4.20	0.9729	0.9714
MLD	6.86	0.8885	0.8446	43.40	0.9978	0.9977	23.04	0.9916	0.9911	0.85	0.9715	0.9695
TEMsum	11.91	0.8838	0.8552	43.78	0.9979	0.9978	22.89	0.9916	0.9911	-3.02	0.9716	0.9710
SALsum	-7.80	0.8963	0.7986	42.57	0.9978	0.9977	21.67	0.9915	0.9908	12.27	0.9755	0.9754
TEMslope	5.83	0.8849	0.8335	44.00	0.9979	0.9978	25.05	0.9920	0.9915	1.08	0.9717	0.9714
SALslope	-0.53	0.9030	0.8159	43.36	0.9978	0.9977	22.51	0.9917	0.9912	11.41	0.9757	0.9753
TEM/SALslope	16.08	0.9019	0.8736	43.39	0.9979	0.9978	22.66	0.9919	0.9914	13.11	0.9765	0.9764

SW IBERIAN COAST

The analysis of the experiments was focused on the differences and the comparison metrics, presented in the previous chapters, between the outputs of Nature Run (NR) and Free Run (FR) over the year 2023. Figure 15 presents the annual evolution of the Instantaneous spatial averages (AVG in Equation 1) of SST over the entire domain for both models. Additionally, the RMSE between the two SST datasets is plotted using the secondary y-axis on the right (red curve), quantifying the differences over time.

The NR and FR exhibit similar seasonal patterns, but their magnitudes vary throughout the year. The RMSE values fluctuate, with higher errors occurring during three distinct periods: early in the year (January–February), mid-summer (July–August), and late in the year as the cold season begins. The largest discrepancies align with the transitions between warm and cold seasons, suggesting that the differences between NR and FR are more pronounced during these periods. To maximize the effectiveness of the OSSE framework, these periods of high discrepancies were selected for conducting the experiments. In an OSSE system, the FR must diverge as much as possible from the NR to ensure that the assimilation of synthetic observations extracted from the NR leads to meaningful improvements of the FR. Therefore, focusing on these specific periods allows for a more rigorous assessment of how observational constraints influence model performance.

To better understand the differences in the behavior of NR and FR, a second instance of the OSSE system was integrated over a shorter period, lasting just over a month. In this case, the integration began with a spin-off simulation, which generated the initial conditions on March 23, 2023. As a result, during the first week, the FR does not have enough time to diverge

significantly from the NR, and they present practically the same results. Figure 16 presents the results of this instance, clearly illustrating this behavior. After the first week, the green curve (NR) exhibits distinct jumps at regular intervals, corresponding to the weekly corrections using CMEMS data, to which the FR is not subjected. This highlights one of the key differences between the two models in the design of the proposed OSSE system, in addition to their differences in grid resolution. Without the weekly corrections, the FR always keeps away from reaching a state that is considered representative of the reality.

Figure 15 - SST comparison between the NR (green line) and FR (black line) integrations over the year 2023. The RMSE between the temperature fields is represented by the red line, with its scale shown on the secondary y-axis (right side of the chart).

Figure 16 - SST comparison between the NR (green line) and FR (black line) integrations over April 2023. The RMSE between the temperature fields is represented by the red line, with its scale shown on the secondary y-axis (right side of the chart).

In addition to analyzing the differences between NR and FR, the first instance of the OSSE system was also used to extract the ensemble members for the data assimilation system integrated into the OSSE framework. Specifically, one FR state was sampled every 25 hours

throughout 2023, resulting in a total of 350 ensemble members. The purpose of this approach is to capture all possible SOMA states within this period and ensure that the assimilation system accurately represents the model's variability.

Before proceeding with the observation experiments, correlation maps of the FR variables were generated to review their relationships. These maps provide insight into key patterns of the model and are presented in Figure 17 and Figure 18. No significant correlation was found between temperature and sea surface height (SSH), and for this reason, this wasn't represented in the maps. However, they indicate a weak positive correlation between SST and currents and a strong negative correlation between SST and salinity, which becomes more pronounced with depth. This pattern is further illustrated in the depth correlation graph of Figure 19.

Building on the second instance of the OSSE system, experiments were conducted to assess the impact of observations on model performance. After one month of integration, the OSSE experiments were carried out on April 27, corresponding to the time when the FR error relative to NR was at its peak, as shown in Figure 16. Each experiment involved incremental amounts of SST synthetic observations extracted from the NR and assimilated into the FR. The number of observations across experiments contained 10, 20, 55, 105, 200, 320, 410, 560, and 1245 points, allowing for a systematic evaluation of how increasing observational density influences the update process.

Figure 17 - Correlation maps computed using a reference point on the surface, the asterisk on the maps, located in the southern coast of the domain. The correlation was computed over time, across 350 ensemble members, relating this fixed point's surface temperature to the rest of the model grid. Maps 1A and 1B show the correlation at the surface for salinity and currents, respectively. Maps 2A and 2B depict the same properties, but at a depth of 100 meters.

Figure 18 - Correlation maps computed using a reference point on the surface, the asterisk on the maps, located in the western coast of the domain. The correlation methodology is the same of what is done in Figure 17. Maps 1A and 1B show the correlation at the surface for salinity and currents, respectively. Maps 2A and 2B depict the same properties, but at a depth of 100 meters.

Figure 19 - Depth-dependent correlation between SST and salinity over time, calculated using the 350 ensemble members. Each curve represents the correlation at different locations within the model domain. The red curve corresponds to the reference point shown in Figure 17 (South Coast), while the blue curve represents the reference point from Figure 18 (West Coast).

Following the update, each experiment was integrated for an additional week (April 27 – May 4). This extended period allowed for an assessment of how long the assimilation effects persisted and how the temperature error responded to different observation densities. As shown in Figure 20, the greater the number of observations used in the update, the smaller the SST error of the FR relative to the NR. Furthermore, it is interesting to note that the improvement associated with each incremental observation is sustained throughout the week. Although the error in an experiment may increase slightly by the end of the integration period, it remains consistently lower than that of the uncorrected FR.

The improvement resulting from the assimilation was not limited to the surface, despite the updates being made solely with synthetic SST. Figure 21 shows the impact of assimilation throughout the water column, showing how the error evolves with depth as the number of observations increases. The RMSE was computed for each model layer

after one week of integration, on May 4. The assimilation effect is perceptible down into deeper layers, to approximately 50 meters, in a way that the greater the number of observations used, the lower the error. Beyond this depth, the impact was insignificant.

Figure 20 - RMSE of SST over time, comparing the Free Run (FR) to the Nature Run (NR) (black line) and the OSSE experiments to the NR (blue lines). The solid blue line represents the OSSE experiment with the highest number of synthetic observations (1245), while the dotted blue lines correspond to experiments with incrementally fewer observations. From the first dotted line closest to the FR downward, each one represents an OSSE experiment using 10, 20, 55, 105, 200, 320, 410, and 560 synthetic observation points, respectively.

While the assimilation of synthetic observations consistently reduces SST error, the improvement is not unlimited. Figure 22 illustrates how the reduction in RMSE becomes less significant beyond approximately 300 observation points. After this threshold, additional observations provide diminishing returns, requiring a substantial increase in data density to achieve further improvements.

Considering the observed saturation effect, additional experiments were conducted to assess whether a targeted spatial distribution of observations could improve the efficiency of the assimilation process. In these new OSSE experiments, the FR domain was segmented into two subregions: the south coast and the west coast. Additionally, incremental numbers of synthetic observations were used in one subregion at a time, with datasets comprising 10, 20, 50, 100, and 200 observations. Concurrently, the counterpart subregion was always maintained at a minimum of 10 observations, thereby ensuring that both areas had at least a minimum of observational coverage.

Figure 21 - Temperature RMSE throughout the water column, computed on May 4, after one week of integration. The color and line scheme follows the same pattern as in Figure 20. However, the number of observations used in the update increases from left to right, starting from the FR black curve.

Figure 22 - RMSE of temperature as a function of the number of synthetic observations used in the update. The black lines represent the RMSE computed only in the surface layer (2D RMSE), while the blue lines correspond to RMSE computed across all model layers (3D RMSE). Solid lines indicate the RMSE immediately after the update on April 27, whereas the dashed lines one week later, on May 4.

The results of the OSSE experiments by subregions are presented in the Taylor diagram in Figure 23. The statistical metrics employed to construct the diagram were obtained following one week of integration for each experiment. The findings clearly suggest that assimilating SST observations from the southern coast results in substantial enhancements to the model's performance. Concentrating observations in this subregion proved to be more effective in maintaining the error in relation to NR. Furthermore, as the number of observations increases, the FR demonstrates a heightened correlation with the NR, thereby underscoring the efficacy of targeted observational placement.

Figure 23 - On the left, a map showing the subregions where the synthetic observations were extracted for each set of experiments. On the right, the Taylor diagram illustrating the results of the OSSE experiments by subregion. The red line and markers represent OSSE experiments where observations were concentrated on the south coast, while the green ones correspond to those with observations on the west coast. The results indicate that increasing the number of observations on the west coast has a minimal effect, whereas higher observation densities on the south coast lead to a more noticeable improvement in model performance.

HARDANGER FJORD SYSTEM

The OSSE conducted with the Hardanger Fjord system model focused on the potential improvement in a fjordic system and especially with respect to improving using observations located at aquaculture sites. The model had not previously been run in an assimilative setup and much of the work focused on getting a stable assimilative model functioning. The results were found to be sensitive to the exact settings and versions of the code, and to get an improvement for any assimilative setup required considerable work. Eventually a functioning version of the code using 10 iterations for the assimilative loop was used as setup where assimilation did not create issues with the initial or boundary conditions, such that improvement from increasing observations could be examined. This resulted in only one post-Nautilus setup being tested.

The different assimilation setups are assessed with respect to the improvement in capturing the fjord and shelf dynamics and stratification, which has a significant controlling impact on the local biology. As a measure of stratification we use the Potential Energy Anomaly, defined as in Simpson (1981) as:

$$Phi = \frac{\int gz(\overline{\rho} - \rho_0)}{D}$$

Where Phi is the potential energy anomaly, D is the water column depth, g is gravity, z is depth, ρ_0 is depth mean density, and ρ is density. This is a measure of the amount of energy required to homogenise the water column and therefore higher values indicate strong stratification, with low values meaning low to no stratification. This is useful as it integrates changes across the water column and has an interpretation relevant to the ecosystem dynamics. First we summarise the change of all statistics using Taylor diagrams and then demonstrate the spatial changes in the stratification statistics, showing the within fjord vs nearshelf performance.

Figure 24 - Taylor diagram illustrating the impact of the pre- and post-Nautilus observation assimilation.

The Taylor diagram shows that the main improvement from assimilation is in the temperature with only a very small impact on the salinity (Figure 24). This however is a domain wide view which is not the most informative for understanding the impact within the fjord. The spatial RMSE (definitions in Deliverable 8.6) shows the error across the domain is highly variable (Figure 25). The changes are concentrated within the fjord areas which is unsurprising as both the region where the assimilation is concentrated and the most dynamic portion of the domain. When we look at the change in PEA the differences are more widespread (Figure 25c), especially within the coastal current which transports water south to north just off the coast. The PEA integrates changes across the water column therefore small changes across a deeper water will be represented.

We now focus on this difference between the fjord and the shelf region within the coastal current and on the changes over time which are not captured by the Taylor diagram or spatial RMSE. We define a region as the Hardanger fjord and another for the shelf (Figure 26). The RMSE error over time (Figure 27) shows that the improvement for the post-Nautilus observations improves over time and is greater later in the run. This is especially clear in the salinity signal (Figure 28) where it can be seen across the water column.

Within the fjord the salinity (and temperature) improves more at depth than at the surface possibly as a consequence of the run off from land having more impact at the surface layer and this already being resolved, as this is not seen in the shelf region.

Figure 25 - Difference in spatial RMSE between pre- and post-Nautilus runs. Negative (blue) indicates an improvement in the post-Nautilus setup.

Figure 26 - The shelf (orange) and fjord (red) regions which are integrated in Figure 27 and the spots indicate the depth profiles shown in Figure 28.

Figure 27 - RMSE error across time in the two selected areas. Black is the temperature RMSE, and blue salinity.

Figure 28 - Depth resolved improvement in salinity RMSE from pre- to post-Nautilus runs. These are at the stations identified in Figure 26.

V. DISCUSSION

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The impact of additional observations, obtained with NAUTILOS technologies, is assessed in the context of current ocean data availability. The average number of in situ observations from Copernicus Mediterranean In Situ TAC database, over the period 2016 - 2019, corresponds to around 78 unique locations per week (see Figure 29). This value represents the upper limit of the pre-NAUTILOS data availability status.

Figure 29 - Number of unique locations of in-situ data in Mediterranean Sea during 2016-2019 (a) and example observations dispersion in January 2016 (b), according to CMEMS In Situ TAC database.

Assuming a future 40% increase in the number of observations (i.e. 110 observations/week) with the contribution of NAUTILOS technologies, Figure 30 illustrates the impact on each assimilated parameter under pre- (AMr78) and post-NAUTILOS (AMr110) ocean observation scenarios.

The model performance is improved for all the considered parameters, including SSH that is not directly related with the profile data. The main positive impact for salinity is evidenced at the first 200 m depth, while after this depth the changes are negligible. In contrast, temperature profile data assimilation has a greater influence at the sea surface and depths below 200 m. In all cases, the improvement with Post-NAUTILOS (AMr110) observations (compared with Pre-NAUTILOS AMr78), appears small, being slight stronger for salinity. Considering the spatial impact of additional observations on the model, the southern Mediterranean Sea is expected to show improved performance, particularly for salinity, as illustrated in Figure 31. However, locally increasing the number of profiles can slightly deteriorate RMSD due to strong corrections around assimilation points, as seen in the temperature RRMSD in the Gulf of Lions.

To define the optimal ocean observation strategy and quantify improvements in data products, a semi-empirical optimization process was developed to select the grid points for assimilation, leading to the highest AM performance. The applied methodology highlighted regions (see Figure 32), where additional data (TEM/SAL profiles) resulted in a stronger model improvement. These areas were characterized by relatively higher model error/bias and/or stronger variability, thus requiring a larger amount of data to be properly captured and may be considered favorable for ocean monitoring. Further enhancements to the optimal position

selection will include incorporating additional criteria, such as covariability, to identify regions with similar behaviour.

Figure 30 - Taylor diagrams for the four assimilated parameters – sea surface height and temperature (SSH , SST) and profiles of temperature and salinity (TEM,SAL) – of five different models runs: free model (FM); assimilation model of SSH/SST data (AMssh/sst); assimilation models of SSH/SST along with SAL/TEM profiles from 78 and 110 randomly selected locations representing Pre-NAUTILOS (AMr78) and Post-NAUTILOS (AMr110) status, respectively; and all grid points assimilation model (AMall) compared to NR.

Figure 31 - RRMSD improvement across different model regions when assimilating TEM/SAL profiles from 110 randomly selected locations (AMr110) compared to 78 locations (AMr78). The figure also includes maps of Mediterranean Sea regions and RRMSD improvement of temperature for the Gulf of Lions.

Figure 32 - Relative RMSD (RRMSD) reduction rate (slope) with increasing number of assimilation points, considering the combined effect (sum) of salinity and temperature.

SW IBERIAN COAST

The Observing System Simulation Experiments conducted with the SOMA high-resolution operational model provide critical insights into the effectiveness of assimilating synthetic SST observations on the area covered by the model. The results highlight a strong seasonal dependence in model discrepancies between the NR and the FR, with the largest RMSE values occurring during transitional periods between warm and cold seasons. The experiments demonstrate that increasing the number of observations consistently reduces the SST error; however, a saturation point is reached beyond approximately 300 observation points, where additional data yield diminishing returns.

While the assimilation primarily targeted surface temperature, its impact extended down to approximately 50 meters in the water column, revealing an influence of surface observations even on subsurface layers. The forecast improvements have also shown to be long-lasting as the RMSE of the assimilated solution is maintained at a lower level for at least one week after assimilation.

The spatial distribution of observations also played a significant role in model improvement. The experiments have shown that synthetic observations obtained along the southern coast led to more substantial performance improvements compared to those obtained along the western coast. The experiments outcomes underscore the importance of both observation density and spatial targeting in optimizing the assimilation process within the OSSE framework.

The experiments have shown the potential for the SOMA operational forecasting to benefit from the new generation of cost-effective observation instruments developed under the NAUTILOS project. Beyond the direct SST updates, the results presented in Figures 17, 18 and 19, suggest a sufficient negative correlation between SST and salinity, particularly strong at subsurface depths. Given that the OSSE system is coupled to an EnOI data assimilation system, this statistical relationship between the variables can be explored and incorporated into a multivariate assimilation framework (Counillon & Bertino, 2009; Turner et al., 2005).

This will allow SST observations to contribute to salinity updates, potentially enhancing the accuracy of the model's representation of water mass properties.

The statistical relationship between SST and salinity requires further investigation, as the circulation in the SOMA region is strongly influenced by winds. In particular, a positive correlation between temperature and salinity was initially expected due to the influence of easterly winds, which transport warm, salty Mediterranean waters toward the Algarve coast. Understanding these dynamics in greater detail will be crucial for effectively implementing multivariate assimilation strategies and optimizing the use of NAUTILOS-developed sensors for improved model forecasts.

As demonstrated by the OSSE experiments, the assimilation of synthetic sea surface temperature (SST) observations significantly improves model forecasts, with a clear dependency on observation density and spatial distribution.

HARDANGER FJORD SYSTEM

The model experiments in the Hardanger fjord highlight the utility of extra observations but also the challenges of both setting up a system which can take into account these observations, and the trade-offs between improving certain areas and variables against degrading the model solution elsewhere.

Getting a functional assimilative system running in the model proved to be harder than anticipated. Although both the ROHO800 and ROHO160 had been run before in a non-assimilative setup, converting to use data assimilation was very technically challenging. The setups were previously run with specific versions of the code which did not have assimilation schemes implemented, and the change to the versions with data assimilation led to model instabilities. The large number of parameters available for tuning in the assimilation schemes (and indeed different schemes – see model setup task 8.6) was also challenging, requiring considerable calibration. This experience underlines that the uptake of additional observations by downstream services depends not only on the availability of the observations but the capacity for the service to take in new types of information. There may be a lag in the technical ability of services to make use of novel and or higher volume observations.

With a working assimilative setup running we ran synthetic experiments assimilating two points representing existing moorings, and with observations at the numerous aquaculture sites in the region. This meant a large increase of assimilation within the complex branching fjords. Overall, the improvements in model skill are modest, but particularly on the stratification measure which combines improvements across the variables and at all depths into one variable, it shows an improvement. The improvements persist through the model run.

We looked at two regions, the fjord and the near shelf, to understand where the improvements are concentrated. All the additional observations were within the fjord area however the stratification in the near shelf shows considerable improvement with the additional observations as the oceanography is highly influenced by the fjord outflow. The changes within the fjord system are highly inhomogeneous with improvements in the main Hardanger fjord channel but sometimes negative effects within the smaller fjords and branches. This is likely due to the coarse resolution of the ROHO800, where a narrow fjord is

represented by only a small number of grid cells. In this case, assimilation may lead to errors as the model struggles to find a compatible solution.

VI. IMPACT OF NAUTILOS-LIKE OBSERVATIONS ON PHYSICAL OCEAN FORECASTING

The OSSE simulations described in this deliverable have put into evidence the remarkable improvement on physical ocean forecasts produced by an increase in the number and type of observations. This conclusion is consistent across European ocean basins, time and space scales. Improvements can be as high as 40% depending on the number and type of new observations added to the model assimilation structures. The low-cost sensors and platforms developed within NAUTILOS are thus foreseen to produce significant improvements in physical oceanic forecasting capacity of the EU.

The physical ocean forecasting improvements are not homogeneous in terms of variables and sampling strategies. It was seen that surface variables (Temperature and Salinity) produce improvements in the model's surface forecasts but are also able to produce improvements along the water column, down to a certain depth (depending of the region being simulated). This is an advantage since surface variables are easier and cheaper to acquire, and in denser coverage, especially if obtained from remote sensing techniques. The improvements are, nevertheless, less remarkable than those obtained from in-depth observations. The use of a combination of surface variables and vertical profiles have produced the best results. Different techniques and platforms were developed in NAUTILOS that allow the acquisition of such variables. Examples are the Deep Ocean CTD, the Animal-borne sensors and the improvements on RS calibration techniques. Improvements in platforms such as the lander and the AUV integration also contribute to these results.

OSSE results also allowed to evaluate the efficiency of ocean observing strategies prior to their deployment. Methodologies were developed to identify the regions where additional observations will lead to the higher impact on ocean forecasting. A common result obtained from the OSSE conducted in this task is that a saturation occurs in the quality of the forecast when massive number of observations are added. This means that beyond a certain point, the inclusion of more observations of the same type do not produce significantly better results. It is therefore important to invest on multiple types of observations, both in terms of variables and in terms of missions. The different platforms tested in NAUTILOS constitute a perfect ecosystem for the development of such combined observation strategies.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results obtained in Task 9.1 and presented above in this report, confirm the foreseen assumption that larger datasets of observed variables would lead to more accurate ocean forecasts. In fact, the application of the OSSE methodology in different regional domains, with different ocean dynamics, using different models and different assimilation methods have all produced the same result: an increase in the number of observations available to assimilate in the models produces an increase in the quality of the forecast.

This conclusion supports the activities developed within NAUTILOS, since lower cost sensors and more efficient platforms will contribute to a more precise and longer-range ocean forecasting systems. A broad estimation of the improvement in forecasting quality produced by a full adoption of NAUTILOS technologies in future ocean observing efforts lies around 40%.

The improvements are variable, depending on the model, the region and the type of variables being assimilated. General recommendations for better ocean forecasting results are:

a) Number of observations

As referred above, generally, the higher the number of observations, the best is the match of the ocean forecast. The improvements however show a saturation with the number of observations, meaning that beyond a certain number of observations the improvement rate is reduced. The number of observations producing saturation varies with the region, the assimilation method and the type of variable.

b) Geographic distribution of the observations

In the Mediterranean study site, results have shown that a uniform distribution of observations consistently outperformed all other arrangements, even with fewer sampling locations, which highlights the importance of the spatial coverage of in situ observations. Thus, future monitoring strategy should take into account existing observational gaps. On the other hand, regions were identified where an increase in the number of sampling points would produce better results. In the SW Iberia study site, for example, regions were identified where a higher concentration of sampling points would produce better results. A good spatial coverage of the entire domain is thus desirable, combined with a reinforcement of observations in specific regions that can be identified by OSSE. OSSE proved thus to be an efficient methodology for the design of monitoring missions.

c) Depth distribution of the observations

Results in the Mediterranean study site have shown that a correct mix of surface observations combined with vertical profiles produced the best results. Since surface observations are normally cheaper and easier to obtain than vertical profiles (especially if RS techniques are used) the definition of the locations and number of vertical profiles needed for a certain accuracy is of utmost importance. Nevertheless, it is worth to mention that even surface variables can produce a significant improvement over depth, dependent of the

assimilation method being used. Again, OSSE are a valuable tool for the design of the monitoring missions.

d) Types of variables

Results have also shown that a mix of variables produce better results than the assimilation of a single variable. In this deliverable only Temperature and Salinity were assimilated, as they are the fundamental variables controlling density, and thus forcing in the ocean. Best results were consistently obtained when both variables were assimilated.

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